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FOREIGN AID, EXTERNAL DEBT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH NEXUS IN WEST AFRICAN COUNTRIES: THE ROLE OF INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY

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Abstract: This study empirically examined the nexus between foreign aid, external debt and economic by assessing the role of governance/institutional quality in 16 West African countries from 2000 to 2024. The study employed panel ARDL, and Dumitrescu & Hurlin panel causality test methods for the analysis. Results indicate that foreign aid exerts positive effect on economic growth but solo external debt negatively affects economic growth. However, institutional quality-external debt interaction has a positive effect on economic growth. This strongly suggests that external debt promotes growth only if judiciously utilized. On the other hand, gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) and foreign direct investment (FDI) all portray positive influence on growth in the long-run. Furthermore, the short-run results reveal that foreign aid is the only significant driver of growth; all other variables do not show significant effects in the short-run. The adjustment mechanism, ECM, is significant negative index confirming that deviations from long-run equilibrium path are corrected over time (about 10% adjustment per period). The findings indicate that economic growth is contingent upon gross capital formation, foreign direct investment, and effective utilization of external debt. These findings have important implications for policymakers in West African countries that are currently facing major fiscal and external imbalances due to high expenditure on infrastructure, worsening trade balance, and financial loss due to the leakages and embezzlements. Thus, there is the need for urgent attention of fiscal authorities of West African economies to use external debts efficiently, reduce fiscal deficits and mitigate external imbalances.

Keywords: Economic Growth, External Debt, Foreign Aid, Governance, FDI

JEL Code: E23, F21, F35, D73

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Typically, developing countries depend largely on external capital inflow for financing developmental projects, largely due to inadequacy in capital formations occasioned by low levels of domestic savings and income. Foreign aid otherwise called Official Development Assistance (ODA), which began in the late 1940s with the initial aim of reconstructing the war-torn economy of Western Europe (Ekpo, 2023), has remained one of the major sources of foreign capital inflow to Less Developed Countries (LDCs) over the years. Provided by governments of developed countries, multilateral institutions and regional development banks, foreign aid comes in the form of

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grants (which do not have to be repaid), concessional loans (which have to be repaid but at a lower interest rate and over a long period) and other non-financial assistance (such as food, technical assistance and peace keeping efforts). Foreign aid operates side-by-side with external borrowing as another source of supporting domestic capital formation in those countries (Juma et al., 2017).

Most developing countries of the world are regarded as being poor not because they do not have the resources but because bulk of their resources (income) are being transferred to meeting the needs of their people with little or nothing left for savings. Hence, low savings rate brings about low investment which in turn begets low growth rate. For this reason, developing nations are left with no option than to go for external borrowings and foreign assistance to bridge the savings-investment gap (Ugochukwu et al., 2016).

A large number of African countries are still battling with debt service problems despite having achieved the debt sustainability level suggested by the highly-indebted poor countries' (HIPC) initiative. The persistence of unsustainable indebtedness amongst many African countries has, therefore, defeated the growth and development. This is largely attributed to poor domestic resources utilization, inadequate debt management capacity, as well as poor institutional and governance quality. Inefficient governance infrastructure has been identified as one of the major barriers to external debt sustainability in Africa (Shittu, et al., 2020). It is not a coincidence thus, that the West Africa had been categorized among the poorest sub-regions in the world (Musibau et al., 2018). Incidentally, researches suggested that foreign capital inflows, especially external debt, could solve this chronic problem (Abdullahi et al., 2025).

Just like foreign capital inflow, institutional quality plays significant role in the development process of low-income countries (Qayyum & Haider, 2013). Availability of funds is not sufficient to run an economy on the right path of growth and development; what matters is good governance/institutional quality that guarantees efficient utilization of the funds, absence of which results in mismanagement and ultimately underdevelopment.

As at today, the specific connection between foreign aid, external debt, institutional quality/governance and economic growth remains unresolved (Nnubia et al., 2022). Many studies examined the relationship and the impact of foreign aid, external debt, and institutional quality/governance on economic growth for developing countries with conflicting findings and have employed different estimation techniques. Some of the studies conclude that foreign aid and external debt stimulate economic growth (Ugochukwu et al., 2016), while others observed that foreign aid and external debt affect economic growth negatively (Mwakalila 2019; Ayenew 2022). Incidentally, Sheikh Ali et. al., 2018; Hassan 2021; Ekpo 2023; Qayyum & Haider, 2013 Jan et al., 2022; and Mba et al., 2012, have all found that foreign aid has positive influence on growth, while Juma et al., 2017; Nnubia et al., 2022; Adamu et al., 2022; and Clinton & Gbenga, 2023 have concluded that foreign aid has negative effect growth. Similarly, the work of Tefera (2020) found mixed relationship between foreign aid and economic growth. Regarding external debt, Juma et al., (2017) concluded that external debt has positive effect on growth; in contrast, Sheikh Ali et., al., 2018; Nnubia et al., 2022; Idehi & Uzonwanne 2021; Jan et al., 2022; Mba et al., 2012; Abdelaziz, et al., 2019; Ashakah, et al., 2025; Manasseh, et al., 2022; Arjun & Mishra, 2024; Asafo, et al., 2019; AL-Tamimi, & Jaradat, 2019, have found that external debt affects growth negatively.

Yet, Qayyum & Haider (2013) observed positive influence of institutional quality/governance interaction on foreign aid, external debt, and economic growth, while, Arjun and Mishra (2024), Hassan (2021) and Ekpo (2023) found negative impact; but Mwakalila (2019) revealed mixed findings. Summarily, existing empirical literature in this area divulges diverse conclusion on foreign aid-external debt-governance combined effect on economic growth.

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Thus, this study reexamines the nexus among foreign aid, external debt and economic growth by controlling for the institutional/governance quality in West African economies, from 2000 to 2024. The remaining parts of the paper consist of four sections. Section two reviews the relevant literature, section three discusses the methodology, section four presents the analysis of results, while section five contains the conclusion and policy recommendations.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The relationship among foreign aid, external debt, institutional quality and economic growth to a recipient country has been investigated by various researchers, focusing on diverse methodologies in different jurisdictions. The review is done in two parts. First part, empirical review on the relationship between foreign aid, external debt and economic growth, while, the second part empirically reviews literature on the mediating role of the institutional/governance quality on foreign aid-external debt-growth nexus.

2.1 Foreign Aid, External Debt and Economic Growth

Mba et al., (2012) examined the interplay of foreign aid, external debt and economic growth. The seemingly unrelated regression estimation (SURE) model to examine the interplay between these variables using Nigerian data was used. Found that foreign aid has positive impact on growth and that external debt has negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Ugochukwu et al. (2016) examined the effect of external borrowing and foreign financial aid on the growth of the Nigerian economy over a period of 34 years from 1980 to 2013. The study employed Ordinary Least Square technique, Johansen Co-integration test and Error Correction Method (ECM) to determine the long-run impact and speed of adjustment. The results show that both foreign aid and external debt have positive and significant effect on economic growth in conformity with the a priori expectation.

Juma et al., (2017) examined the effect of the external borrowing and foreign aid on economic growth in Tanzania over the period of 1992 to 2014 using ECM approach. The results reveal the presence of long-run cointegration among variables. The results shows that the foreign reserves, exchange rate and external borrowing have positive relationship and significant with economic growth while foreign aid has a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth. The result also shows that the foreign reserves, external borrowing, and exchange rate have a positive relationship and significant with economic growth, while foreign aid has negative relationship but insignificant with economic growth in the short-run.

Sheikh et al., (2018) assessed the effects of foreign debt and foreign aid on economic growth in Somalia from 1970 to 2014. The ordinary least squares (OLS) method was used and basic model assumption tests were also employed. The results of the study show that, in Somalia, foreign debt has an insignificant effect on economic growth, while the foreign aid has positive significant effect on economic growth. The results also indicate that the cointegration method confirms the incidence of long-run association among the variables.

Nnubia et al., (2022) examined the nexus between the external borrowing, foreign aid and economic growth in Nigeria. The data used were secondary data and were drawn from 1986 to 2016. The study applied ex post facto research design. The data collected were analysed using Pearson Correlation Matrix. The study revealed that economic growth proxied by Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has a positive association with foreign reserves, foreign aid and openness of the economy; but has negative association with external debts at 5% level of significance.

Jan et al., (2022) in their study used the annual data from 1990 to 2018 and applies autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) Co-integration technique to check the impact of foreign aid and external debt on socio-economic

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development of Pakistan. The empirical finding of the study shows that foreign aid is positively related with economic development in short run while; external debt has a negative impact on economic development in long run.

In another clime, Ismael (2024) examined the effect of external debt on economic growth in three developing countries. Utilizing 189 responses in those countries, the research utilized Chi-square tests, Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS), and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), in the process of the analysis. The findings reveal that moderate external debt impacts positively on economic growth but excessive debt reduces growth.

2.2 Foreign Aid, External Debt, Institutional Quality and Economic Growth

Qayyum and Haider (2013) investigates the impact of foreign aid, external debt and governance on economic growth by extending the Ramsey-Cass-Koopman's growth model in an open economy framework. Steady-state and short run analysis show that external debt and foreign aid do not affect the growth rate of consumption but have level impact on consumption. Foreign aid and governance encourage the economic growth but external debt creates a burden on the economy. Therefore, it is argued that improvements in the quality of governance will stimulate the output and consumption rapidly and it acts like a catalyst.

Mwakalila, (2019) analysed the impact of foreign aid and external debt on economic growth in Africa, considering governance indicators. Panel data was collected for 39 countries in Africa spanning across 20 years from 1996 to 2016. Ordinary Least Square (OLS), Fixed Effects, and System Generalised Method of Moment (GMM) estimation techniques were used for the analysis. The results first suggest that in general, both foreign aid and external debt have a negative impact on the African economy but some African countries that have strong governance indicators are the ones that benefit from foreign aid and loans in improving their economy. Second, foreign aid from the U.S. has a detrimental, negative impact on the African economy compared to that from EU countries. Finally, foreign aid brings more harm to lower income countries compared to upper and lower-middle-income countries.

Shittu et al., (2020) examined the relevance of governance on the relationship between external debt and economic growth in selected five sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries from 1996 to 2016. The study uses the fully-modified OLS technique. The findings confirm a non-linear relationship between external debt and economic growth with a positive net effect of \$5.05 increase in economic performance for a US\$ rise in external debt. While the index of governance depicts a negative association with economic growth, the indicators show mixed results. Ogbo et al., (2020) examined the role of institutional quality on economic growth and reduction of inequality in Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted and data were collected through primary and secondary sources. Population of the study was 600 businesses across Nigeria. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that the bottlenecks facing businesses in accessing loans have significant effects on business creation in Nigeria. The study concluded that lack of policies and interventions are not the problems for small businesses to obtaining funds from government, but effectiveness and efficiency of these interventions and policies.

Simidi et al., (2021) investigated effect of governance on the relationship between external debt financing and economic growth in the EAC member countries using the Baron and Kenny moderation testing approach. Result revealed that, the relationship between external debt and sustainable economic growth is positive but not statistically significant. The relationship between governance and sustainable economic growth is positive and statistically significant. The interaction term between governance and external debt exhibits a statistically

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significant relationship with sustainable economic growth which is however negative due to the negative governance indices in the region.

Ring et al., (2021) utilized GMM panel data analysis, covering twenty-three samples of countries from 2011 to 2014, to examine the nexus between external debt and economic growth where institutional quality acts as a moderator. The samples for the study are divided into two groups consisting of low and high governance groups of countries. Findings report the importance of institutional quality as a moderator in the relationship between external debt and economic growth for both samples of study. The results confirm that, despite the importance of good governance practices, prescribing the right policy is crucial to avoid the negative impact of the wrong policy prescription on economic growth. Overall, the study suggests good debt management and feasible policy prescriptions are the keys to controlling external debt.

Ekpo (2023) examined the effect of foreign aid and aid-institutional quality interaction on economic growth in Nigeria for the period (1981 - 2022) using FMOLS method. The result of the study shows that foreign aid (ODA) exerted positive but insignificant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The aid-institutional quality interaction variable, the ODA interaction with corruption index (ODA*CPI), showed negative relationship with economic growth which suggests that weak institution, especially corruption, had constrained the positive effect of ODA on economic growth in Nigeria.

Abdullahi et al., (2025) investigates the effects of external debt on economic growth, and assesses whether effective governance has any influence in this relationship from 1996 to 2024 in Nigeria. Data are analysed using Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds test to cointegration. Findings revealed that, an increase in external debt negatively affects economic growth in the short to long-run in Nigeria. Incidentally, deterioration in governance and political stability impact negatively on growth in Nigeria, both in the short-run and long-run. Research studies conducted on the relationships between foreign aid, external debt, institutional quality/governance and economic growth have however remained inconclusive as some studies exerted to positive, negative, U-shaped and dual causality relationships respectively. Hence, findings on the relationship between foreign aid' external debt and economic growth still remain largely controversial, it is clear that studies on the moderating effect of institutional quality on the relationship are few and far between.

Considering the above works which take diverse countries, methodology, and choice of variables, this is the first study that contemplates the nexus between foreign aid, external debt and economic growth by considering the interaction of institutional quality/governance indicators in 16 West African Countries.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This article adopts the Big Push and Debt Overhang theories as the frameworks upon which the study is anchored. Growth economists over time have postulated different theories of growth including the “Big Push” model which have differing implications for foreign aid. According to the big push model, Africa is poor because it is stuck in a poverty trap. To get out of the poverty trap, African countries need a huge aid finance increase.

The basic argument behind the Big Push is that coordination problems in the context that increasing returns create the possibility of multiple equilibria. That is, a poor country could be caught in a low equilibrium (poverty trap). However, government intervention can potentially solve the coordination problem and push the economy into the better equilibrium which allows for a takeoff into sustained growth. Foreign aid can finance the big push. Government's subsidy policies and financing of big infrastructure are typical examples of government attempting

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to coordinate the economy. However, these efforts in most developing economies are marred by rent seeking and corruption (Abdullahi et al., 2025).

Debt Overhang theory on the other hand, argues that large levels of accumulated debt cause to lower growth. There is some likelihood that, in the future, debt will be larger than the country's repayment capability, so, expected debt-service costs will discourage further domestic and foreign investment and thus harm growth (Musibau et al., 2018).

This study investigates the nexus between foreign aid, external debt and economic growth by considering the interaction of institutional quality/governance in West African Countries.

3.2 Data Description

The panel nature of the data is obtained by pooling the cross section (N = 16) with the time-series (T = 25) dimensions, thus, bringing the sample size to 400 observations. The variables involved are real gross domestic product (GDP) as the dependent variable, while, foreign aid (FA), external debt (ED), governance indicators (GOV), and interaction between governance indicators and external debt (GOV*ED) as independent variables. The data is sourced from the World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI) and World Bank’s World Governance Indicators (WGI) database. The samples of study consist of 16 West African countries, which consists Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone and Togo, for the period of 2000 to 2024. According to WGI, institutional quality/governance is measured in terms of six dimensions including voice and accountability, political stability and absence of violence, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law and control of corruption (Shittu et al., 2020). Following the World Bank’s definitions, the measurement, description and the expected coefficient value of each variable is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Variable Name, Definition and Source and Priori Expectation

Variable	Definition	Data source	Priori Expectation
GDP (Y)	GDP (current US\$)	World Bank(WDI)	+/-
Foreign aid (FA)	Net official development assistance (ODA)	World Bank (WDI)	+/-
External Debt (ED)	External debt stocks (current US\$)	World Bank (WDI)	+/-
Gross Capital Formation (GCF)	Gross capital formation (% of GDP)	World Bank (WDI)	+
Foreign Direct Investment	Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)	World Bank (WDI)	+
Governance Indicator			
Control over corruption	Control over corruption	(WGI)	+
Accountability	Voice and accountability	(WGI)	+
Politics	Political stability and absence of violence	(WGI)	+

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Politics	Political stability and absence of violence	(WGI)	+
Equality	Regulatory quality	(WGI)	+
Rule of law	Rule of law	(WGI)	+
Government effectiveness	Government Effectiveness	(WGI)	+

Source: Authors' compilation

3.3 Model Specification

Going by the above economic theories, the equations constructed for this research is modelled and modified after the works of Shittu et al., (2020), Arjun & Mishra (2024) and Ring et al., (2021) to investigate the relationship between foreign aid, external debt and economic growth by considering the interaction of institutional quality/governance indicators in West African Countries from 2000 to 2024.

This relationship can be modelled as in equation (1).

$$GDP_t = f(FA_t, ED_t, GCF_t, FDI_t, GOV_t, GOV * ED_t) \tag{1}$$

In this model, where, GDP_t is real gross domestic product, FA_t foreign aid, ED_t is external debt, GCF_t is gross capital formation (% of GDP), FDI_t is foreign direct investment (% of GDP), GOV_t consists of a set of governance indicators (as measured by World Governance Indicators), which are voice and accountability, control of corruption, political stability, no violence, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, and the rule of law. The moderating effect of institutional quality is measured by the interaction between each of the six components of governance indicators, and $GOV * ED_t$ is the interaction of governance indicators and external debt.

In order to assess the nexus between foreign aid, external debt, economic growth and the role of interaction effect of institutional quality/governance indicators, this study applies panel autoregressive distributed lag (panel ARDL) approach under the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) framework advanced by Pesaran et al. (1999). Panel ARDL method has several advantages. (i) It is capable in confirming the long-term cointegration relationship exists between the variables, even if they are in a different order of integration, that is, $I(0)$, or $I(1)$. (ii) It observes potential convergence towards the long-run equilibrium while taking into account the dynamic heterogeneity of the adjustment process. (iii) Since the sample period consist of a panel of 16 countries ($N=16$), for 25 years ($T=25$) and the number of years considered is much more than the number of countries, GMM method is not appropriate in our study (Arjun & Mishra, 2024). Therefore, the panel ARDL method is used with three estimators which are: the pooled mean group (PMG), the mean group (MG), and the dynamic fixed effect (DFE). Nevertheless, Hausman (1979), hereafter Hausman test statistics, is used to choose the most suitable model amongst the PMG, MG, and DFE approaches. The null of the Hausman test indicates that variation between PMG and MG or between PMG and DFE estimation is not substantial. If the null does not get rejected, that is, the p-value is greater than 5%, the PMG estimator will be used. Considering the Hausman test findings, it is perceived that there is a similar long-run slope across countries.

Panel ARDL model follows a two-step procedure where the first step observes the incidence of cointegration between the variables. If the co-integration nexus is established in the first step, the subsequent step includes the estimation of long-run and short-run coefficients. The short-run restrictions could be imposed by approximating an error correction model related to the long-run estimations.

The main model of the Panel ARDL method aims to establish the relationship between the variables. Equation 2 is expressed as an error correction model equation by further grouping the variables in levels:

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$$y_{i,t} = \alpha_i + \sum_{i=1}^K \gamma_i^{(k)} Y_{i,t-k} + \sum_{i=1}^K \beta_i^{(k)} X_{i,t-k} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Where the constant term is $K \in N^+$, the lag parameter is denoted by $K \in N^*$, and $\beta_i^1, \dots, \beta_i^k, \alpha_i, \gamma_i^k, \varepsilon_{i,t}$ and β_i^k designate the slope of the coefficient. The null hypothesis posits the absence of any homogeneous Granger causal association in the panel data, while the alternative hypothesis asserts the existence of at least one Granger causal relationship. Both null and alternative hypotheses can be written as follows:

$$H_0 = \beta_i = 0$$

$$H_1 = \begin{cases} \beta_i \neq 0 \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, N \\ \beta_i \neq 0 \forall i = N_1 + 1, N_2 + 2, \dots, N \end{cases}$$

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis of the results obtained from the various techniques employed. The analysis begins with the summary statistics of the variables in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	LOGGDP	LOGFA	LOGED	GCF	FDI	GOV	LOGGOV*ED
Mean	22.69522	19.96449	21.87739	23.80494	4.777183	31.92323	24.94800
Median	22.63847	20.07526	21.60003	22.46581	2.527058	31.03644	24.80944
Maximum	27.07622	22.57984	25.41239	52.66984	103.3374	93.02938	28.47339
Minimum	19.78510	17.64617	19.37955	4.562497	-11.19173	0.007063	19.11871
Std. Dev.	1.405675	0.983160	1.266734	8.693255	9.498634	20.84543	1.325452
Skewness	0.583621	-0.247145	0.643688	0.821771	7.060225	0.507387	0.110749
Kurtosis	3.536069	2.524721	2.957596	3.585038	63.39611	2.720617	4.386622
Jarque-Bera	25.36603	7.229521	25.50919	46.79377	59148.81	17.03276	30.31615
Probability	0.000003	0.026923	0.000003	0.000000	0.000000	0.000200	0.000000
Sum	8374.538	7366.898	8072.758	8784.021	1762.781	11779.67	9205.813
Sum Sq. Dev.	727.1396	355.7104	590.4981	27810.75	33202.45	159907.7	646.5111
Observations	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

The descriptive statistics of the variables shown in Table 2 above indicate that, Economic Growth (LOGGDP) has the Mean value of 22.70 and Standard deviation value of 1.41 which is relatively volatile compared to other variables. The Foreign Aid (LOGFA) Mean value of 19.96 and Standard Deviation of 0.98 reported low variability. External Debt (LOGED) Mean value of 21.88 and Standard Deviation value of 1.27 shows moderate variability. But the Gross Capital Formation (GCF) has Mean value of 23.80 and Standard Deviation value of 8.69 which shows very high variability. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Mean value of 4.78 and Standard Deviation value of 9.50 revealed highly volatile. Governance (GOV) Mean value of 31.92 and Standard Deviation value of 20.85 report large variability. However, Governance and External Debt Interaction (LOGGOV*ED) has the Mean value of 24.95 and Standard Deviation value of 1.33 which relatively stable.

The economic growth (LOGGDP), foreign aid (LOGFA), external debt (LOGED), and governance and external debt interaction show relatively low variability. The volatile variables were Gross capital formation (GCF),

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foreign direct investment (FDI), and governance (GOV) exhibit high fluctuations. None of the variables are normally distributed (all Jarque-Bera probabilities range from 0.000000 - 0.026923 are significant).

FDI is the most unstable variable with extreme skewness and kurtosis, while economic growth is relatively stable but still deviates from normality. Governance and capital formation show wide variability, which may explain their strong causal influence on growth in your causality test.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of the Variables

Correlation Matrix							
Probability	LGGDP	LGFA	LGED	GCF	FDI	GOV	LGGOV*ED
LOGGDP	1.000						
LOGFA	0.809	1.000					
	0.000						
LOGED	0.885	0.701	1.000				
	0.000	0.000					
GCF	0.123	0.104	0.168	1.000			
	0.019	0.046	0.0012				
FDI	-0.142	0.024	-0.188	0.239	1.000		
	0.006	0.643	0.0003	0.000			
GOV	-0.395	-0.352	-0.328	-0.045	0.025	1.000	
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.388	0.627		
LGGOV*ED	0.389	0.342	0.565	0.048	-0.112	0.411	1.000
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.355	0.031	0.000	

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

The correlation matrix of the variables in Table 3 above indicates that, Economic Growth (LOGGDP) has a strong positive correlation with foreign aid (LOGFA) of 0.81 and external debt (LOGED) 0.88 which means economic growth is closely associated with aid inflows and debt accumulation. Weak positive correlation with gross capital formation (GCF) of 0.12 revealed that investment is linked to growth but less strongly. The negative correlation with foreign direct investment (FDI) of -0.14 and governance (GOV) -0.39 reported that, the higher economic growth is associated with lower FDI inflows and weaker governance scores. The positive correlation with governance and debt interaction (LGGOV*ED) of 0.39 per cent means the growth rises when governance interacts with external debt.

Economic Growth is strongly correlated with foreign aid and external debt, suggesting aid and borrowing are major drivers of growth patterns. Governance shows negative correlation with growth, aid, and debt, implying that reliance on aid and debt may undermine institutional quality. FDI is negatively correlated with growth and debt, indicating that high debt burdens discourage foreign investors. Capital formation is positively linked to FDI, reinforcing the investment–FDI nexus. Governance and debt interaction positively correlates with growth, highlighting that governance moderates the impact of debt on growth.

The correlation matrix suggests a growth model heavily dependent on aid and debt, but at the cost of governance quality and FDI inflows. Strong institutions and balanced debt management are crucial to sustain growth without undermining investment and governance.

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Table 4: LLC and IPS unit root tests results

Variable	Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC)			Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS)		
	Level	First Difference	Order of Integration	Level	First Difference	Order of Integration
LOGGDP	-5.99723	-	I (0)	-	-8.12421	I (1)
LOGFA	-5.11833	-	I (0)	1.23362	-	I (0)
LOGED	1.27011	-5.83680	I (1)	2.99722	-5.66683	I (1)
FDI	-0.40044	-5.98345	I (1)	3.98070	-	I (0)
GCF	-0.45378	-11.0366	I (1)	1.79101	-11.8401	I (1)
GOV	-1.88170	-	I (0)	0.65863	-	I (0)
LOGGOV*ED	-0.44076	-3.27122	I (1)	1.67635	-7.25223	I (1)
				0.65021		

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

Table 4 above summarizes the findings of the unit root-test of the variables in interest. The findings of the Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC) unit root-test indicates stationarity of three variables at levels I(0) that is economic growth (LOGGDP), foreign aid (LOGFA) and governance (GOV). However, the outcome of Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) unit root-test results revealed stationarity of three variables at levels I(0) which includes: foreign aid (LOGFA), foreign direct investment (FDI) and governance (GOV). At the first difference, all considered variables turnout to be stationary as suggested by LLC and IPS. The overall findings advocate that variables are integrated in mixed order, that is I(0) or I(1). However, none of the variable is found to be integrated of second order I(2). These conditions allow us to apply the application of panel ARDL model for further estimation.

Table 5: Panel ARDL Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Long Run Equation				
LOGFA	0.116400	0.108789	1.069956	0.2857
LOGED	-0.571098	0.286573	-1.992853**	0.0474
GCF	0.031442	0.008004	3.928131*	0.0001
FDI	0.007355	0.004149	1.772495	0.0776
GOV	-0.029035	0.008924	-3.253548*	0.0013
LOGGOV*ED	0.669667	0.289673	2.311805**	0.0217
Short Run Equation				
D(LOGFA)	0.086512	0.036421	2.375340*	0.0183
D(LOGED)	0.131641	0.129702	1.014952	0.3112
D(GCF)	0.005968	0.006131	0.973444	0.3313
D(FDI)	0.056991	0.057975	0.983022	0.3266
D(GOV)	-0.005464	0.007914	-0.690400	0.4906
D(LOGGOV*ED)	-0.171589	0.150503	-1.140099	0.2554

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ECM (-1)	-0.102348	0.035011	-2.923279*	0.0038
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Note: *, **, and*** Signify statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively.

ARDL lag structure (1,1,1,1,1).

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

The ARDL Long-Run and Short-Run equation results of the nexus between foreign aid, external debt, governance/institutional quality and economic growth in West African Countries shown in Table 5 above. The long-run result reported that, foreign aid (LOGFA) has a positive but statistically insignificant effect on economic growth. This means a per cent increase in log of foreign aid (LOGFA) would lead to 0.116 per cent increase to economic growth in the long run while, the log of External Debt (LOGED) result exerted a negative but statistically significant effect to economic growth; this implies that, a per cent increase in log of external debt would lead economic growth decrease by 0.571 per cent. The external debt negatively affects growth in the long-run. This result confirming debt overhang concerns theory which is not contrary with the expectation.

The Gross Capital Formation (GCF) has a positive and statistically significant impact to economic growth. The result revealed that; a unit increase in Gross Capital Formation (GCF) would lead to 0.031 per cent increase to economic growth. This means, investment strongly and positively drives long-run economic growth. However, the result of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) revealed positive but insignificant effect to economic growth. This implies that, a unit increase in FDI, would lead to economic growth increase by 0.007 per cent. FDI contributes positively to growth, though its effect is weak.

Shockingly, the result of Governance (GOV) indicators has a negative but statistically significant effect on economic growth; this contrary with priori expectation. The result implies that, a unit increase in governance, would lead economic growth decrease by 0.029 per cent in the long-run, possibly reflecting weak institutional quality or governance inefficiencies. But interestingly, the result of Governance and External Debt Interaction (LOGGOV*ED) implies that, a per cent increase in the interaction terms (LOGGOV*ED), would lead to economic growth increase by 0.6697 per cent. The interaction between governance and debt positively affects growth, suggesting that good governance can mitigate debt’s negative impact.

The Short-Run Equation Results reported that, change in log of Foreign Aid (LOGFA) has significant positive effect on economic growth, which implies that, a per cent increase in change in log of foreign aid, would lead to 0.086 increases in economic growth. Foreign aid positively contributes to growth in the short run; this is in line with long-run equation. However, the change in log of External Debt (LOGED) does not have significant but positive effect to economic growth. The finding implies that; economic growth increase by 0.131 per cent should change in log of external debt increased by one per cent. The short-run debt has no significant effect on growth and this is not contrary with long-run equation.

The change in Gross Capital Formation (GCF) and change in Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) results has positive effect but statistically not significant to economic growth. Unit increase in change in gross capital formation, would lead to economic growth increase by 0.006 per cent, implies that, the short-run investment does not significantly drive growth. The result of change in FDI revealed that, a unit increase in change in FDI would lead to economic growth increase by 0.05 per cent in the short-run equation. This means FDI has no short-run impact on growth.

Uninterestingly, change in Governance (GOV) and change in log of Governance and External Debt Interaction (LOGGOV*ED) has negative statistically insignificant impact to economic growth in the short-run equation which is contrary to the priori expectation sign. The result of change in Governance (GOV) implies that, a unit

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increase in change in Governance (GOV), would lead to economic growth decrease by 0.006 per cent. The governance/institutional quality indicators does not significantly and positively affect growth in the short run. Furthermore, the change in log of Governance and External Debt Interaction (LOGGOV*ED) result reported that, economic growth would decrease by 0.172 per cent, should change in log of Governance and External Debt Interaction (LOGGOV*ED) increase by one per cent in the short-run equation. This revealed no short-run effect of governance /institutional quality and debt interaction but, this is contrary with long-equation.

The coefficient of Error Correction Term (ECM) has negative sign, that is, -0.10 and probability value of 0.0038 (significant). The negative and significant ECM confirms long-run equilibrium. About 10% of disequilibrium is corrected each period.

Table 6: Dumitrescu-Hurlin Panel Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	W-Stat.	Z-Stat.	Prob.	Conclusion
LOGFA→LOGGDP	1.88425	-0.57345	0.5663	LOGFA does not cause LOGGDP
LOGGDP→ LOGFA	3.95932	2.67996	0.0074*	LOGGDP cause LOGFA
LOGED → LOGGDP	1.47545	-1.21439	0.2246	LOGED does not cause LOGGDP
LOGGDP → LOGED	3.23653	1.54673	0.1219	LOGGDP does not cause LOGED
GCF → LOGGDP	3.64216	2.18270	0.0291**	GCF cause LOGGDP
LOGGDP → GCF	2.36582	0.18160	0.8559	LOGGDP does not cause GCF
FDI → LOGGDP	2.45550	0.32219	0.7473	FDI does not cause LOGGDP
LOGGDP → FDI	2.86157	0.95886	0.3376	LOGGDP does not cause FDI
GOV → LOGGDP	3.53119	2.00871	0.0446**	GOV cause LOGGDP
LOGGDP → GOV	3.31022	1.66227	0.0965	LOGGDP cause GOV
LOGOV*ED → LOGGDP	2.00771	-0.43619	0.6627	LGGOV*ED does not cause LGDP
LOGGDP → LOGOV*ED	3.94084	2.42719	0.0152**	LOGGDP cause LOGGOV*ED

Note: *, **, and*** Signify statistical significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively.

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

After understanding the relation among foreign aid, external debt, governance/institutional quality, and economic growth, the Dumitrescu-Hurlin Granger Causality test is conducted to check the robustness of the panel ARDL results. Results are reported in Table 6 above. The null hypothesis of Dumitrescu-Hurlin Granger causality test indicates that, each individual determinant does not homogeneously cause economic growth and vice-versa. The variable such as Foreign Aid (LOGFA), External Debt (LOGED), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and Governance–Debt Interaction (LOGGOV*ED) does not homogeneously granger cause economic growth. The tests statistics (W-stat and Z-stat) for all variables are found be insignificant except Gross Capital Formation (GCF) and Governance (GOV) indicating rejection of the null hypothesis. It advocates that Gross Capital Formation (GCF) including governance/institutional quality indicators, do Granger cause economic growth. The reverse causality observed between Economic growth influences foreign aid and the governance–debt interaction. No causality found between External debt and FDI show no significant causal relationship with growth. This study does not find bidirectional causality between any two combinations of variables, which endorses robustness in endogeneity bias. Thus, these findings confirm the conclusions drawn from the panel ARDL test (Dumitrescu and Hurlin, 2012). The Gross capital formation (investment) and governance significantly cause economic growth.

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5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

West African countries had been ranked among the poorest sub-regions in the world due to inadequate resources to bridge the gap between savings and investments, to bridge these gaps, the scholars suggested foreign capital flow especially foreign aid and external debt will solve these chronic problems aimed at fostering economic growth and development. However, many developing countries have failed to effectively utilize these external capital inflows to progress their countries. This study examines the relationship between foreign aid, external debt, economic growth, and role governance/institutional quality across 16 West African countries using annual data from 2000 to 2024. The overall findings of Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC) unit root-test advocate that variables are integrated in mixed order, that is $I(0)$ or $I(1)$. These conditions allow us applied the application of panel ARDL model in the estimation.

The fundamental conclusion of this paper is that, the long-run drivers of growth were foreign aid gross capital formation, FDI (weakly), and governance and external debt interaction positively influences growth, while external debt and governance alone negatively affect growth. Furthermore, in the short-run, foreign aid is the only significant short-run driver of growth, while other variables show no short-run effects. The adjustment mechanism confirms that deviations from equilibrium are corrected over time, at an average of 10% per period.

Unidirectional causality was observed between economic growth and foreign aid, as well as between governance-external debt interaction and growth, while external debt and FDI show no significant causal relationship with growth. However, no bidirectional causality is observed between the variables of this study.

Economic growth is investment-led and governance-conditioned in the long run, while foreign aid plays a short-run supportive role. Debt undermines growth unless moderated by governance quality, highlighting the importance of strong institutions in managing external borrowing.

5.1 Policy Recommendations

This paper provides some concrete suggestions/implications for policy-makers as follows:

Firstly, the escalation of external debt in the Western African sub-region needs to be curtailed through sound debt management policies by the concerned authorities. This is necessary because debt alone may be counterproductive to growth and development. Debt management authorities in the region should determine the optimum level of external debt which should be guided by needs, absorption capacity, servicing ability and sustainability.

Also, political authorities in the region need to make extensive policies to ensure effective utilization of the debt in productive investments. The authorities should strive to reduce/stop misappropriation, diversion and or embezzlement of the funds by strengthening the quality of political institutions and general governance, particularly in the areas of rule of law and regulatory quality.

Furthermore, West African economies should reduce reliance on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and focus on domestic sources of capital formation. The results indicate that FDI does not have significant effect on growth in the region. As such, the respective economies should look inward to mobilize additional savings for investments. A synergy between the economies to establish common pool for capital and investment should be encouraged. This will be revolutionary as gross fixed capital formation will go a long way in stimulating growth as indicated in the results.

Lastly, West African economies should give priority to fiscal discipline and reduction in fiscal deficits to reduce external borrowings. Excessive cost of governance and general financial losses must have to be curtailed to ensure efficiency in the use of the available resources and income in those countries. This will help reduce reliance on foreign sources of capital.

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